

Research Paper

Emergence of Rural Markets in India - Opportunities, Threats and Innovations

Author

Dr. Himanshu Agarwal

Associate Professor, Faculty of Commerce and Business Administration,
D. N. (P.G.) College, Meerut, UP, India. e: dr_hagarwal@yahoo.com m: 09412125893

Abstract

Rural India, which was earlier ignored by marketers, is now attracting more and more companies towards it. Marketers now see a need to tap this segment of the population where they see a huge scope for marketing. But only those companies that understand the rural psyche of the masses can win over the rural consumers and bring out innovative products, which serve their needs. And, in the changing business environment, the rural customer is very active and quality conscious. Urban markets are becoming competitive increasingly and, perhaps, getting saturated. The rural market in India is not a separate entity in itself and it is highly influenced by the sociological and behavioral factors operating in the country. About 285 million live in urban India whereas 741.6 million reside in rural areas, constituting 72.22 per cent of India's population resides in its 6, 27,000 villages. Size of rural market is estimated to be 42 million households and rural market has been growing at five times the pace of the urban market. The core of a scientific approach is to understand the market opportunities for rural products along with the country's development priorities and to chalk out a strategy where rural industries have an important role to play. While rural products are forced to increasingly become part of global supply chains, these products need to adapt themselves, not only according to the changing tastes of the national market, but also according to changes in tastes in the international market. Therefore, a process is essential to explore the market linkages and capacity building for SHGs through a bottom up approach and continuous dialogue with stakeholders of rural enterprise. This process should ensure the participation of rural people as consumers and producers in the globalization mechanism, with better livelihoods and global access to markets. The real challenge of building a sustainable market linkage starts here.

Key Words: *Fast Moving Consumer Goods, Rural consumer, Marketing Strategy, Urban consumers, Indian Economy, Opportunities, Innovations*

1. INTRODUCTION

A large amount of our population lives in the villages. Moreover, most of the population that resides in urban areas is also connected to the villages whether it is a matter of household edibles or a linkage in any way. Presently, more than 72 per cent of the total population lives in the villages due to their source of income which is either agricultural or related to it. Therefore, everyone has to go to the rural areas to fulfill needs or to complete business cycle. The reach of Media and Information Technology has pushed up the graph of the rural people awareness about the likings, the choices, the availability, the behaviour and the paying capacity. India is now seeing a dramatic shift towards consumption and prosperity in rural households. Rural population is nearly three times the urban, therefore, Rural Consumers have become the prime target market for consumer durable and non-durable products, food, construction, electrical, electronics, automobiles, banks, insurance companies and other sectors besides hundred per cent of agri-input products such as seeds, fertilizers, pesticides and farm machinery.

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population where they see a huge scope for marketing. But only those companies that understand the rural psyche of the masses can win over the rural consumers and bring out innovative products, which serve their needs. And, in the changing business environment, the rural customer has become more active and quality conscious and urban markets are becoming competitive increasingly, perhaps, getting saturated. Following points may be put forth in support of the rural markets-

- (a) Rural spending is now less dependent on farm income, which now constitutes less than 50 per cent of the total rural income. Income remittances from migrant rural populations and increases in non-farm activities such as trading and agro-processing are boosting non-farm income.
- (b) The increase in procurement prices (the minimum price that farmers earn on produce sold to the government) is bringing more money in the hands of the rural population.
- (c) The government has increased spending in rural areas to accelerate the development process.
- (d) Improved access to finance and institutional credit has brought greater cash inflows to rural households.
- (e) Policy measures such as the waiver of agricultural loans and the Mahatama Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MNREGA), which guarantees 150 days of employment to one member of every rural household, have helped to reduce rural under-employment and raised wages.

Table 1: Macroeconomic Indicators

Sl No.	Particulars	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14*
1	Rate of Growth of GDP	8.6	8.9	6.7	4.5	4.7
2	WPI based Inflation (%)	3.8	9.6	8.9	7.4	6.0
3	Fiscal Deficit (% GDP)	6.39	5.1	5.7	4.9	4.5
4	Per Capita Income	44345	53331	60972	67839	74920

*Latest Available

The macroeconomic data in table 1 clearly points to the soaring potential of India's nonurban markets. Rural Consumer Price Index is 139.7 while urban Consumer Price Index is 136.0. It shows more spending and more demand in rural buying patterns. But, the statistics do not give clues to how interested business leaders might be in the opportunities at hand. Nor do they say whether companies are prepared to make the kind of investments that are required to unlock long-term value from rural markets. Are businesses executives who do express interest in the nation's rural opportunities typically looking at them as consumer markets or as sources of raw materials and labour—or both? Do they believe they have what it takes to understand what exactly rural consumers want now and in future? And have business leaders really begun to identify the challenges and drivers that will influence their approaches to rural opportunities?

To get answers to questions such as these, Accenture commissioned a quantitative survey of 109 large and mid-sized multinational and domestic companies with revenues ranging from US\$200 million to more than US\$10 billion. Here are the key findings of that survey being quoted as under:

- a) The overarching trend that emerged from the survey findings is that businesses are confident about the opportunities that rural India has to offer.

- b) Survey findings indicate that corporate leaders believe a rural presence can help strengthen their overall competitiveness.
- c) Rural markets encompass eager consumers who want to share the fruits of India's industrial growth. More than half of the senior executives surveyed were keen to tap rural areas' new segments of consumers.
- d) Many consumers in rural areas lack the prejudices that make their urban counterparts resistant to change. They are keen to experiment with new products, new services and new processes.
- e) Around 74 per cent of respondents reported that lack of proper linkages for roads, railways and telecom infrastructure are big hindrances. Another 40 per cent cited the lack of skilled talent and 34 per cent highlighted fragmented demand patterns as key challenges. Other barriers to profitability and scalability include the lack of granular information on rural markets and consumers, and limited access to financing options.
- f) More than 60 per cent of respondents identified the size of the necessary upfront investments as the biggest hurdle towards establishing rural operations.

The companies should also strive to give more focus to the rural market in order to make it a market leader. This can happen only with the firm commitment of the top management and extension of full support to the marketing personnel by each and every department of any organization, which targets the rural market.

2. NEED OF THE STUDY

Rural Markets are defined as those segments of overall market of Indian economy, which are distinct from the other types of markets like stock market, commodity markets or Labour economics. The so-called urban markets are crowded and saturated and the share of agriculture in GDP is going down but India still lives in her villages. Such a potential market was being ignored by corporate sector and small and medium industries. Hence, it is proposed to study the opportunities, threats and innovations of rural market with a special reference to Indian Rural Market.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Rural markets, as part of an economy, have untapped potential. There are several threats confronting the effort to fully explore rural markets. The concept of rural markets in India is still in evolving shape, and the sector poses a variety of threats, including understanding the dynamics of the rural markets and opportunities to supply and innovation to the rural consumers. The objectives of this study include observing the opportunities, threats and innovations of Indian Rural Markets reviewing the literature of rural markets and rural marketing, outlining the emergence of rural markets with respect to innovative practices adopted by companies of different segments like FMCG, Automobiles, Retail etc.

4. HYPOTHESES

Author envisions opportunities, threats and innovation for unexplored rural markets in India.

5. METHODOLOGY

The method of study is descriptive. The data collected through secondary sources. The study surveys from Internet, textbooks, reports, journals and from self- knowledge. Here, Rural Markets of India means the market situated in Rural Areas of India (the Republic of India in Indian Sub-continent).

6. REVIEW OF LITRATURE

Kaur Manpreet (2013) attempted to find out the various initiatives taken by HUL to reach the rural consumer. Hindustan Unilever is the pioneer and largest player in India's FMCG market. HUL was the first company to step into the Indian rural marketing. HUL started its first effort towards going rural 1960's onwards, through indirect coverage of accessible rural market through its urban network stockists and distributors. HUL proactively engaged in rural development in 1976 with Integrated Rural Development Programme in Etah district of Uttar Pradesh. In 1990, HUL launched 'Operation Streamline' for distribution of products to inaccessible rural markets with High potential using unconventional transport like bullock carts, tractors and bicycles and appointed rural distributors and star sellers. In 2000, HUL started Project Shakti to reach inaccessible low potential rural markets. This project has reached 100,000 villages. HUL embarked upon Project Samuriddhi in 2003 to create sustainable villages in Dadra and Nagar Haveli. Today HUL's products touch the lives of two out of every three Indians.

Kotni VV Devi Prasad (2012) proposed to undertake this study to find out various ways to tap the potential rural markets. The main aim of this study was to observe the potentiality of Indian Rural Markets and finding out various problems are being faced by rural markets. This paper attempted to provide a brief literature on rural marketing and finally offers policy recommendations for better performance of rural markets by adopting SWOT analysis matrix to rural markets.

Priya Lakshmi and Vandana Bajpai (2011) stated that the objectives of rural management is to organize, develop and utilize the available at optimal level to proper utilization and productivity of resources, in such a manner that the entire rural population may be benefited by it and increase the production and consumption to increase Indian economy. Rural management also helps to enhance living standard rural people. Since independence, the Government has initiated certain plans for the betterment of rural people. Upgrading rural market is one way to improve access to marketing opportunities. Early to pre-independent, Indian rural people played very important role in Indian independent movement and make India free from British regime, but rural people did not get much attention from Indian govt. and other business organization, to understand them and fulfill their needs and wants. Although India is an agriculture based country and Indian economy is totally based upon agriculture and villagers, even they have being ignored. Since 1990 the wave of L.P.G. 2 (Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization) has changed the face of Indian rural markets and still is in its transition period, due cut throat competition in urban markets, more market saturation and negative demand.

Sakkthivel (2005) in her study "Effectiveness of Sachets in Modifying Rural Consumer's buying behavior and their Consumption Pattern," examined the effectiveness of small sachets in modifying consumer's buying behavior and found out the quantity and frequency of purchase of products by rural consumers. The purposive survey was conducted among 150 consumers who resided in Tumkur district in Karnataka and the sampling technique used was judgment sampling

7. EMERGENCE OF RURAL MARKET

The rural market in India is not a separate entity in itself and it is highly influenced by the sociological and behavioral factors operating in the country. About 285 million population live in urban India whereas 741.6 million reside in rural areas, constituting 72.22 per cent of India's population resides in its 6, 27,000 villages. Size of rural market is

estimated to be 42 million households and rural market has been growing at five times the pace of the urban market.

Rural areas are also known as 'Countryside' or a 'village' in India. 'Rural' is defined by various agencies separately as given below:

- a) The National Sample Survey Organization (NSSO) defines rural as follows:
 - An area with a population density of up to 400 per square kilometer,
 - Villages with clear surveyed boundaries but no municipal board,
 - A minimum of 75 per cent of male working population involved in agriculture and allied activities.
- b) RBI defines rural areas as those areas with a population of less than 49,000 (tier -3 to tier-6 cities). It is generally said that the rural areas house up to 70 per cent of India's population. Rural India shares a good part to India's GDP through agriculture, self-employment, services, construction etc. As per a strict measure used by the National Sample Survey in its 63rd round, called monthly per capita expenditure, rural expenditure accounts for 55 per cent of total national monthly expenditure. The rural population currently accounts for one-third of the total Indian FMCG sales.

The definition of the word 'rural' in a market like India is very amorphous. There are multiple versions of the same idea, which are followed by different entities. Even in the rural marketing space, there is not one concrete definition. Different brands define 'rural' according to their product and service offerings. According to various studies, around 12.2 per cent of the world's population lives in rural India, this also indicates that 29 per cent of the world's rural population lives here. The green revolution in India made the rural areas to consume a large quantity of industrial and urban manufactured products. In this context, a special marketing strategy, namely, rural marketing has taken shape. Sometimes, rural marketing is confused with agricultural marketing – the later denotes marketing of produce of the rural areas to the urban consumers or industrial consumers, whereas rural marketing involves delivering manufactured or processed inputs or services to rural producers or consumers.

Although, India's rural markets present such opportunities, that companies, are seeking to register high-performance, cannot afford to ignore. But the size and scale of those markets (three-fourths of the country's approximately 1.1 billion people live in villages) have been offset by concerns about the profitability of these markets and the durability of rural demand. There are several strong regional and macroeconomic reasons for greater confidence. And, there is a growing body of statistics to demonstrate that rural markets, fueled in part by rising purchasing power, hold real prospects for profitable growth across a wide range of industry sectors. There are a number of myths regarding the immense potential of the Indian rural market. Some common myths are as follows:

- Rural Market penetration is not beneficial;
- Rural Consumers will take just what is given to them;
- Rural Consumers will only buy really cheap mass-market brands;
- One family one brand;
- Distribution drives rural sales;
- The Rural Market is an Extension of the Urban Market; and
- Perception and attitude of rural people are same.

But, the reality differs. Rural consumers are influenced by rationality, personal experience, and the level of utility, that is derived from the consumption, etc. The clever,

gimmick advertisements do no work with rural consumers. Their buying behavior is influenced by experience of their own friends, relative and family members. Above all, quality of the product and its easy availability are the primary and vital determinants of the consumer buying behavior. Rural consumers are very much attached to an influence by touch and feel aspect of any promotional activity. So, rural marketers need to have an open mind, and sensitize themselves to understand the rural consumer. The Following tables put the above said views in terms of data:

Table-2
Distribution of National Population in Rural and Urban Areas

Distribution	Population			Population percentage
	Persons	Males	Females	
Rural	741,660,293	381,141,184	360,519,109	72.22
Urban	285,354,954	150,135,894	135,219,060	27.78
Total	1,027,015,247	531,277,078	495,738,169	100.00

Table-3
Top Ten Indian States with Comparatively Highest Rural Population

Rank	State	Rural Population
1	Uttar Pradesh	13,15,40,230
2	Bihar	7,41,99,596
3	West Bengal	5,77,34,690
4	Maharashtra	5,57,32,513
5	Andhra Pradesh	5,52,23,944
6	Madhya Pradesh	4,42,82,528
7	Rajasthan	4,32,67,678
8	Tamil Nadu	3,48,69,286
9	Karnataka	3,48,14,100
10	Gujarat	3,16,97,615

Table 4
Estimated annual size of the Indian Rural Market

Sector	Turnover
FMCG	Rs.50,000 cr
Durables	Rs. 5,000 cr
Agri-inputs incl. Tractors)	Rs.45,000 cr
Two / Four Wheelers	Rs. 8,000 cr
Total	Rs.1,08,000 cr

8. ACCESSIBILITY OF RURAL MARKET

Accessibility of rural market has become easy through improved infrastructural facilities like transportation, communication, and TV penetration and Information

Technology. The following points can be put forth in favour of Rural Market potential in India:

- i. Around 72.22 per cent people live in rural areas and 27.78 per cent people live in urban areas.
- ii. According to a study done by MART, a specialist in rural marketing and rural development consultancy, 53 per cent of FMCG sales come from rural areas, as do 59 per cent of consumer durable sales.
- iii. One-third of the total number of luxury goods is sold in rural India.
- iv. Two-thirds of the middle-income households are in rural India.

However, corporate enterprises have also played a significant role in the development of rural markets. Their timely intervention into the rural markets, their appropriate planning, their perception and identification of the growth of rural markets, and the use of marketing strategies, have equally contributed for the progress of rural markets.

There are various reasons owing to which the companies want to access the rural market. These are as follows:

- a) Untapped Potential: It offers a great chance for different branded goods as well as services for the larger number of customers and the untapped potential. It is estimated by HLL that out of five lakhs villages in India, only one lakh has been tapped so far, which goes on to indicate the market potential of the rural market.
- b) Market Size: The size of India's rural market, stated as the percentage of world population is 12.2 per cent. This means 12.2 per cent of the world's consumers live in rural India. In India rural households form about 72.22 per cent of the total households and this constitutes a huge market by any standard.
- c) Current Consumption: The purchase and consumption of certain durable and non-durables by consumers in rural areas is more than that in urban areas. Some of the products for which the demand in rural areas is more than that of urban areas are sewing machines, radios, wristwatches, bicycles, etc.
- d) Social and Behavioral Influences in the Rural Markets of India: The rural consumer is influenced by the environment and by his wants and perceptions. Understanding the social and attitudinal influences on rural consumer behavior is important to the marketers, as these serve as a guide to decide on product offering, pricing, distribution, media, and message, in effect, forming the rural marketing strategy.
- e) Attitude to Quality and Price: Small pack sizes get acceptance in markets, which can pay only a small price because of the nature of income receipts. A landless laborer may get a small amount of money everyday, so he buys his provisions daily and does not have a big amount to spend. He will, therefore, buy something that has a small unit price. But, it is not true that only cheap brands sell in rural markets.
- f) Brand Preference and Loyalty: It is useful to have a good understanding for the purchase behavior of the consumer to take decision for the rural market. In as many as 18 product categories, consumption of branded items account for 80 per cent of sales. These are not always national brands, regional or locally manufactured brands also have good sales. This indicates the potential for national brands if they can find a way to package their offering to compete effectively with regional brands.

Therefore, the industries must play a catalytic role to cope with these situations and should also train the entrepreneurs to develop their managerial and IT skills. On the other hand, the products of the existing and popular brand also stand as threat to the rural products. These global giants (brand) may try to suppress the rural products in the markets with its communication hype. Therefore, developing alternative and additional market linkages for these products is an absolute necessity. Moreover, the low volumes of rural products, high operating cost, high attrition, and absence of local know-how and relationships may also create problem in the process.

9. OPPORTUNITIES AND THREATS FOR RURAL MARKETS

Rural Marketing is defined as any marketing activity in which the one dominant participant is from a rural area. Rural areas of the country are areas that are not urbanized, though when large areas are described country towns and smaller cities are also included. They have a low population density, and typically much of the land is devoted to agriculture. And, the most important one is Marketing strategy that worked for urban markets do not necessarily work for the rural ones. Following are some important differences in urban and rural markets:

- i. Rural individual's access to media channels is limited and in the case of broadband the comparable upload and download speed may be slower. Online shopping is seen as a solution by many but will be dependent on broadband speed.
- ii. Rural consumers will be slower to pick up trends or brands but will remain loyal when accepted. Rural consumers need personal touch and nearness.
- iii. Many rural areas sometimes have to rely on a lesser extent agricultural incomes from seasonal crops. This means there will be more disposable income at certain times with rural businesses and employees.
- iv. Brands with demonstrable local, rural, environmental and/or social credibility stand a better chance.

A-Opportunities:

1. Good Previous Records: In 2011-12, LIC sold 57 per cent of its policies in rural India. Of two million BSNL mobile connections, 52.3 per cent are in small towns / villages. Of the 6.27 lakh villages, 5.72 lakh have a Village Public Telephone (VPT). 44 million Kisan Credit Cards have been issued (against 22 million credit-plus-debit cards in urban), with cumulative credit of Rs. 992 billion resulting in tremendous liquidity. 42 million rural households (HHs) are availing banking services in comparison to 27 million urban HHs. Investment in formal savings instruments is 6.6 million HHs in rural and 6.7 million HHs in urban.

2. Infrastructure is improving rapidly: In 66 years only, 40per cent villages have been connected by road, in next 10 years another 30per cent would be connected. More than 90per cent villages are electrified, though only 44per cent rural homes have electric connections.

Rural telephone density has gone up by 300 per cent in the last 10 years; every 1000+ pop is connected by STD. Social indicators have improved a lot between 2001 and 2010 -Number of "pucca" houses doubled from 41 per cent to 63 per cent and "kuccha" houses halved (40 per cent to 22 per cent). Percentage of BPL families declined from 46per cent to 27 per cent. Rural literacy level improved from 36 per cent to 59per cent. Low penetration rates in rural areas, so there are many marketing opportunities –

Durables	Urban	Rural	Total (per cent of Rural HH)
CTV	30.4	4.8	12.1
Refrigerator	33.5	3.5	12.0

FMCGs	Urban	Rural	Total (per cent of Rural HH)
Shampoo	66.3	35.2	44.2
Toothpaste	82.2	44.9	55.6

3. Size is increasing: Estimated annual size of the rural market is more than 750 million people.

FMCG	Rs. 70,000 Crore
Durables	Rs. 5,500 Crore
Agricultural-Inputs (including tractors)	Rs. 48,000 Crore
2 / 4 Wheelers	Rs. 8,400 Crore

4. Government support in upgradation: Government is providing subsidies to the villagers to use other source of energy like Solar System and is now being used in large amount. Growing rural infrastructure through Government initiatives has worked a lot. On the other hand, setting up of channels like e-choupals by companies like ITC has created distinct approach.

5. More rural development initiatives:

- Increasing agricultural productivity leading to growth of rural disposable income.
- Lowering of difference between taste of urban and rural customers.
- Good Monsoons in the last couple of years.

B- Threats

Rural markets in India have untouched potential. There are several threats that confront the effort to fully explore rural markets. The concept of rural markets in India is still in evolving shape, and the sector poses a variety of threats.

- a) Distribution costs and non- availability of retail outlets are major problems faced by the marketers.
- b) The success of a brand in the Indian rural market is as unpredictable as anything. Many brands, which should have been successful, have failed miserably at later stage. This is because most firms try to extend marketing plans that they use in urban areas to the rural markets.
- c) The unique consumption patterns, tastes, and needs of the rural consumers should be analyzed at the product planning stage so that they match the needs of the rural people.
- d) Generating effective demand for manufactured foods are a Hercules task for the companies those go rural. Because the rural population has a very Low level of exposure to different product categories and product brands.

- e) Inadequate infrastructure facilities (lack of physical distribution, roads warehouses and media availability) as the rural markets are highly dispersed and thinly populated markets.
- f) Low per capita and poor standards of living, social, economic and cultural backwardness of the rural masses.
- g) Cultural gap between urban-based marketers and rural consumers.
- h) Low literacy rate and Traditional outlook of rural consumers due to which they are resistant to change. Their buying decision is slow and delayed.
- i) Demand in rural market depends on the agricultural situation as it is the main source of income. Again agriculture depends on monsoon. So buying capacity of rural consumers varies and it becomes difficult to predict demand.
- j) Retailers pushing imitation or fake products in place of branded ones for better commission.
- k) Lack of proper physical communication facilities:
 - Inadequate Media coverage for rural communication
 - Many language and Dialects
 - Market organization & staff
- l) Traditional methods of rural marketing make an interesting study and they ought to be analyzed carefully to draw relevant conclusions.

In Indian context, rural marketing is a difficult subject. For a business organization, rural marketing is beset with a number of problems. The prices of rural marketing pose many problems due to the vastness of the country and a high potentiality for providing an effective marketing system. It is now unanimously accepted that the rural salesmanship in India has been insufficient and inadequate and out of proportion to the agriculture revolution. This calls for strong bias in favour of raising the rural demand as against the urban demand. The traditional marketing activities of promotion, distribution, sales and servicing, undertaken so far in the urban and semi-urban contexts, are to be extended to cover a much wider area in a rural environment by introducing appropriate innovation, selection and adoption.

Therefore, marketers need to understand the social dynamics and attitude variations within each village though nationally it follows a consistent pattern. The rural markets involve additional cost both in terms of promotion and distribution. In rural marketing, often it is not promotion of a brand that is crucial, but creating an awareness concerning a particular product field, for instance, fertilizers and pesticides. Urban and semi-urban based salesmen are not able to tap the full potential in the villages. The mind set of rural population is remarkably different from those of urban population. Here, it may be suggested that the marketers may select and employ the educated unemployed from villages.

10. INNOVATIVE PRACTICES ADOPTED BY COMPANIES

The Indian rural market has a huge demand base and offers great opportunities to marketers. Two-thirds of Indian consumers live in rural areas and almost half of the national income is generated here. The reasons for heading into the rural areas are fairly clear. Most of the FMCG companies used to treat rural markets as adjuncts to their urban Strong holds and rural consumers as a homogeneous mass without segmenting them into target markets and positioning brands appropriately. The winning strategy instead is to focus on their core

competency such as technological expertise to design specific products for the rural economy.

Along with the cultural dynamics, the needs and latent feelings of the rural people have to be well understood before launching products in rural segments. Marketers would do well to first understand this and then designing products accordingly. The rural market remains quite price-sensitive and thus squeezing costs at every stage is of vital importance. However, not all traditional strategies need to work and the need is to generate creative ideas. A very significant step for change could be an effort to directly tap the haats, mandis, melas and local bazaars which provide an opportunity of promoting the brand in front of a large congregation of rural consumers.

a) e-Choupal: It is an initiative of ITC Limited, a large multi business conglomerate in India, to link directly with rural farmers via the Internet for procurement of agricultural and aquaculture products like soybeans, wheat, coffee, and prawns. E-Choupal was conceived to tackle the challenges posed by the unique features of Indian agriculture, characterized by fragmented farms, weak infrastructure and the involvement of numerous intermediaries. The programme involves the installation of computers with Internet access in rural areas of India to offer farmers up-to-date marketing and agricultural information.

b) Bhoomi: Bhoomi is a project jointly funded by the Government of India and the Government of Karnataka to digitize the paper land records and create a software mechanism to control changes to the land registry in Karnataka. The project was designed to eliminate the long- standing problem of inefficiency and corruption in the maintenance of land records at dispersed and poorly supervised and audited block-level offices known as "taluka" offices in South India and "tehsildar" offices in North India. The project development and implementation was done by National Informatics Centre. Implementation of Land record computerization has been difficult in India. Bhoomi succeeded because there was a champion who worked a 15-hour day for over 12 months, devoting 80per cent of his time to the project. Minimizing resistance from staff by harnessing political support was an important contributory factor. Extensive training coupled with a participatory style also helped to diminish resistance."

c) N-Logue: n-Logue Communications (P) Ltd has taken over the much-talked about Warna wired village project. Vinay Kore, chairman of the Warna Cooperatives will be the local service provider and partnering n-Logue's project here. The Warna project will be getting a new lease of life with this tie-up. This will be the fifth site for the n-Logue project in Maharashtra. Two projects are already being implemented in Baramati with the Vidya Institute of Information Technology and in Pabal with Vigyan Ashram as its local service provider. The company has also signed up with Nobile Technology Solutions for deploying the technology in Aurangabad and with Alphetetics Business Machines Pvt Ltd for Niphad. n- Logue's projects have taken off in Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu, the n-Logue founder and head of department of electrical engineering, IIT Chennai, Dr Ashok Jhunjhunwala said. n- Logue is promoted by the Telecommunications and Computer Network group (TeNet) in IIT, Chennai which developed the corDECT wireless in local loop technology. "This technology has been deployed in 1500 towns in India and in 12 countries outside,"

d) TARahaat: It is a for-profit social enterprise which delivers education, information, services and other opportunities to rural areas, through internet. It is an initiative of Development Alternatives Group, a New Delhi-based non-profit organization,

which was established in 1983 to create large scale sustainable livelihoods. TARAhaat mostly utilizes India's existing telecom infrastructure, such as telephone lines, but these offer low-speed erratic connectivity. A satellite-based alternative solution was tried out, but that is a not-so-economical solution. The most interesting aspect of TARAhaat is its strong focus on developing products and information content relevant to rural consumers. Additionally, TARAhaat provides extensive support, both financial and knowledge, for rural entrepreneurs setting up its franchises. It also encourages its franchisees to come up with new product ideas. TARAhaat enjoys the advantage of being associated with Development Alternatives, which is one of India's oldest organizations working on sustainable development. This association brings an in-depth knowledge of the needs of rural India and experience in handling the challenges. This has helped TARAhaat achieve success in creating economic and social value.

e) Drishtee: Drishtee establishes kiosks that offer affordable Internet access, consumer products and community services to rural Indian villages. Local entrepreneurs manage these kiosks. The Drishtee network is vast, with more than 14,000 entrepreneurs registered to date and kiosks operating in three states. India's 638,000 villages are home to more than 775 million people. And nearly half of this population survives on less than \$1 a day. Surveys have found that the average villager earns \$90 a year and spends 80 per cent of that income on subsistence items like healthcare, housing and food. Drishtee builds service kiosks to provide villages with access to Internet connections, consumer products and critical community services. Offerings include computer education, English education, e-governance, health check-ups, and a wide range of consumer goods such as groceries, cosmetics, mobile phone recharge coupons, and rechargeable torches and batteries. Local entrepreneurs run the Drishtee kiosks. Through its low-cost, direct delivery rural supply chain network, Drishtee has created significant cost and time savings for villagers and an effective channel for enterprises to sell products and services. Drishtee has a strong presence in three states – Assam, Bihar and Uttar Pradesh – and more than 14,000 entrepreneurs currently registered in the network.

f) Community Information Centre: The Community Information Centre Townsville Inc (CIC) is a not-for-profit community organisation funded primarily by Townsville City Council. The Centre was established in 1976 as a volunteer organisation and has since continued to provide information to residents, a wide range of community groups and government departments. The CIC provides a comprehensive information and referral service. The service is free (except for cost of publications), confidential and available to any member of the community. The types of requests received by the CIC are many and varied. They cover a diversity of issues, including employment services, tenancy rights, family and individual crisis referral, recreational activities, disability access and services, and new residents' information.

g) Mitra- Lok Mitra and Jan Mitra: With a view to deploy IT for the benefit of citizens of the states, Government of Rajasthan launched two citizen friendly projects in the year 2002, namely LokMitra and JanMitra. Mitra integrated LokMitra & JanMitra:e-Mitra Project integrates LokMitra and JanMitra initiatives under a single umbrella to bring together all the departments under one single umbrella and give citizens of the state a multi-service single-window experience.

h) HKB (Hariyali Kisaan Bazaar): It is an innovative effort aimed at empowering farmers and meeting the needs of rural households by providing access to agricultural products, services and retail. Established in the countryside, the stores offer:

- quality inputs (fertilizers, seeds, pesticides, tools, veterinary products, animal feed, irrigation items, diesel, petrol)
- agronomic services with teams of extension workers and agronomists providing advice to customers
- financial products (crop insurance, credit, banking, investments, money transfers)

Each HKB centre caters to communities within a 25-30 km perimeter and impacts the life of about 20,000 households. HKB's business model is to provide targeted services to farmers in remote regions. As such, it is a pioneering project because it contributes to rural and agricultural development and food security while being a profitable business venture. It also reinforces the need for farming communities to have access to information and technology. In June 2009, DSCL announced the plan to add 300 stores to the existing 300 by 2012. The group is currently present in eight states and is India's largest rural retail chain.

i) HUL (Project Shakti): Project Shakti is a rural distribution initiative that targets small villages. The project benefits HUL by enhancing its direct rural reach and also creates livelihood opportunities for underprivileged rural women. Shakti is the initiative that combines social responsibility, sustainability, and business strategy. Shakti model is very strong and sustainable because it is the best way we can give it back to the society through supporting our cause of 'empowering underprivileged rural women' along with making business sense. Shakti started with 17 women in two states. Today, it provides livelihood enhancing opportunities to about 45,000 women in 15 Indian states and provides access to quality products across 100,000+ villages and over 3 million households every month.

6. CONCLUSION

India's rural markets offer several opportunities. The urban-rural split in consumer spending stands at 9: 11, even in Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) will have witnessing more than 50 per cent of growth in its Rural and Semi-Urban Segments in 2012 which in totality is projected to grow at an CAGR of 10 per cent to carry forward its market size to over Rs.1,06,300 crore from present level of Rs. 87,900 crore, according to an analysis carried out by the Associated Chambers of Commerce and Industry of India (ASSOCHAM). With increasing incomes and awareness levels, the needs and consumption in small town India are converging with larger, more affluent towns. Though, there are fewer affluent and middle class consumers in these smaller towns their tendency to trade-up is often higher than that of their big-city counterparts. This paper examines how some innovative practices, adopted by government of India and the corporate world helps to strengthen the rural market with their innovation and creativity tapping the Indian rural market.

Because of this sustainable market linkages, rural producers can participate in the benefits of globalization and will also develop their capacity to maintain global quality standard. Nonetheless, it creates new stakeholders for the industry sector. And subsequently, they become part of the firms' core businesses. The involvement of the private /industry sector at the rural product and market development can also provide opportunities for the development of new services and values to the customers, which will find application in the developed markets. It will be worth mentioning that building a sustainable market linkage through industry's intervention will also empower the rural mass (producers, farmers & entrepreneurs) to cope with socio-economic problems in the rural

society and will ensure economic self –reliance. Only consistent performance can convince the skeptics.

The core of a scientific approach is to understand the market opportunities for rural products along with the country's development priorities and to chalk out a strategy where rural industries have an important role to play. While rural products are forced to increasingly become part of global supply chains, these products need to adapt themselves, not only according to the changing tastes of the national rural market, but also according to changes in tastes in the international market. Therefore, a process is essential to explore the market linkages and capacity building for SHGs through a bottom up approach and continuous dialogue with stakeholders of rural enterprise. This process should ensure the participation of rural people as consumers and producers in the globalization mechanism, with better livelihoods and global access to markets. The real challenge of building a sustainable market linkage starts here.

Today, the rural marketers have become more focused on consumer choice and requirements. This calls for Segmenting, Targeting and Positioning (STP). Since the rural market in India began to grow.

However, companies face many challenges in tackling the rural markets. Some of the important factors being an understanding of the rural customers' needs are liable distribution channel, and an effective marketing communication strategy to put their message across to the rural consumer. Coming up with some innovative techniques in distribution, and marketing of products in rural India, can make these companies to earn greater profits, market share etc.

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